

“THANKS TO MY COMMUNITY AROUND ME”: UNDERREPRESENTED STUDENT
EXPERIENCES UTILIZING COMMUNITY CULTURAL WEALTH TO APPLY TO
SPEECH-
LANGUAGE PATHOLOGY MASTER’S-LEVEL PROGRAMS

by

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Less than ten percent of speech-language pathologists (SLPs) are non-White despite the significant and growing population of racially marginalized people in the United States. With the demand for SLPs increasing, there is a need to facilitate access to the profession. The present study used the asset-based Community Cultural Wealth framework to analyze longitudinal survey data from a series of open-ended questions to investigate the sources of cultural capital that underrepresented students leverage to navigate the graduate school application process to master's level speech pathology programs. Findings indicated that students developed a wide network and reflected on personal social injustices to facilitate the knowledge and self-efficacy needed to navigate the application process. These processes activated and cultivated the several interrelated forms of community cultural wealth underrepresented students relied on. This work suggests that developing lateral and vertical networks helps underrepresented students develop a community that fosters encouragement and an exchange of resources to persevere in the application process. This research identified several programs and resources which have been beneficial for applicants, directing universities to potential funding areas to demystify the application process for underrepresented students and increasing diversity in the speech language pathology workforce. Programs such as ASHA STEP Mentoring and student support groups are useful in fostering social, navigational, familial, and aspirational capital.

Keywords: application, underrepresented, graduate degree, resilience

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The demographics of the current speech-language pathology workforce does not align with the demographics of people which they serve. White-identifying speech-language pathologists (SLPs) comprise 91.3% of the workforce (American Speech-Language Hearing Association 2022) despite 59.3% of the United States population identifying as “White alone, not Hispanic or Latino” (U.S. Census Bureau 2021). Workforce diversity is an important component in bridging health equity and providing culturally competent services to clients (Jackson and Gracia 2014) so there is a critical need to balance racial representation in the field of speech-language pathology. Especially as demand for the profession is projected to increase by 21% by 2031 (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics 2022), the field needs to facilitate access to the career for underrepresented students.

To become a practicing and certified SLP in the United States, one must earn a master’s degree in speech-language pathology. The U.S. Census Bureau (2017) describes master’s degree attainment of adults ages 25 and older as 9.5% among all racial and ethnic groups in the US. This statistic, however, is lower in American Indian or Alaska Native (5.1%), Black (7.1%), Hispanic (3.9%), and Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander (5.3%) populations. This disparity also exists in other careers that require a master’s degree, such as counseling and social work (Baker, Gaulke, and Smith 2015; Kim 2022), yet none are as racially homogeneous as speech-language pathology.

Considering the stark contrast in racial and ethnic diversity between the U.S. population and the current demographics of SLPs, research has evaluated the barriers in educational

pathways which determine who can pursue a graduate degree in speech-language pathology and eventually become a SLP (Fuse 2018; Kovacs 2022). While current research uses a deficit-lens to identify challenges for underrepresented students, few studies have evaluated the assets that underrepresented students use when applying to graduate school for clinical programs such as speech-language pathology.

This study examines the critical period of applying to master's programs in speech-language pathology with a focus on underrepresented undergraduate students in California. Drawing on a series of four mixed-methods surveys over the span of twelve months from 2021 to 2022, the study investigates the assets derived from underrepresented students' cultural capital which are utilized to apply to graduate school. The collection and analysis of this data allows us to understand how underrepresented undergraduate students have amassed community cultural wealth (Yosso 2005) to navigate the graduate school application process for speech pathology programs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Barriers in the Application Process

Growing literature on underrepresented students pursuing careers in speech pathology uses a deficit-lens to identify institutional barriers that pose challenges for students applying to graduate school. Fuse (2018) found that finances, socioeconomic status, and college-educated familial role models influenced student decisions when applying to graduate schools for communication sciences and disorders. Indeed, the most significant barriers in managing the application process were securing financial aid, obtaining letters of recommendation, and identifying necessary application information. Moreover, students from lower socioeconomic status spent less time studying for tests and earned lower grade point averages (GPA) than their

peers who self-identified with high socioeconomic status. Underrepresented populations applying to SLP graduate programs are also significantly more likely to have transcripts and Graduate Record Examination (GRE) scores received beyond the 28 day window after the application deadline (Kovacs 2022). Thus, underrepresented students are less likely to have the financial means or knowledge of the required application materials when they are moving through the application process.

Challenges to applying also include barriers in the required application materials. The GRE is a frequently assessed quantitative factor. In nursing programs, the GRE served as a significant barrier to application, especially for underrepresented nurses, despite the fact that the GRE is not an effective indicator for academic ability and success in nursing graduate programs (Katz et al. 2009). The GRE not only discourages students from applying, but also has poor predictive validity on student success in graduate school. Conflating the equity issues of the GRE with a global pandemic only heightened the disadvantages posed before applicants. Although the GRE provided an at-home exam option, marginalized students faced hurdles such as the necessity of high-speed internet access and possession of a laptop or desktop (Millar 2020). Requiring this “objective” admission requirement does not equitably represent a student’s potential for success in a graduate program.

The graduate school application requirements also include qualitative barriers. Pruitt and Isaac (1985) identified discriminatory practices such as recruitment procedures and subjective admission standards (including letters of recommendation). Recruitment for graduate programs is hindered by institutional and systemic issues. Since speech pathologists are predominantly White, underrepresented students are less likely to have role models in the field who could provide guidance navigating the application process (Richburg 2022). When it comes to

applying, students may struggle to make valuable connections with White faculty for letters of recommendation and may not have faculty of color in their department. Outside of the quantitative barriers, social interactions with faculty and experiences within the field can create or relieve obstacles in applying.

Support Systems

Even in the face of barriers, underrepresented students have support systems along their educational journey. This network of support ranges from family members to structured mentorship programs, providing students with emotional support and resources to navigate the graduate school application process.

Studies on Latino experiences applying to graduate school identified sources of support for the applicants. Undergraduate research programs and support from institutional agents proved to be crucial to applicants as these supports decoded the graduate school application and provided guidance on the graduate school choice process (Ramirez 2011). Importantly, institutional agents included faculty, university staff, and siblings. Familial and social capital was bred through siblings' knowledge of maneuvering through higher education and through the familial values rooted in education. Similarly, first-generation, Latino students in a student pathway program experienced reduced application stress or confusion with early exposure to information about graduate school, access to role models and familial support, as well as having a community of peers with similar ambitions fosters an environment where students are committed to applying to graduate school (Martinez 2018). These findings reveal the interconnected nature of navigational, familial, social, and aspirational capital tied to bridging the pipeline to graduate school for first-generation, Latino students.

Mentorship serves as another source of support, as found in another allied health field. In the field of occupational therapy, the need for inter-cultural and professional support for underrepresented students may be fostered by individual mentor-mentee relationships and connections with national organizations specifically for people of color. These mentorships facilitated recruitment for occupational therapy students of color to persist in education and enter the field as a clinician (Ford, Smith, and Banister 2021). Educational institutions can support students by providing mentoring opportunities and opportunities to connect with role models who look like them and have similar backgrounds.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study used the community cultural wealth (CCW) theoretical framework (Yosso 2005). Community cultural wealth is an asset-based perspective on Communities of Color that draws from Pierre Bourdieu's (1984) theory of social and cultural capital and Critical Race Theory (CRT) to steer away from the deficit-based lens that views Communities of Color as environments filled with cultural disadvantages. The Bourdieuan framework provides an understanding of human capital, however, it emphasizes the deficits of those who purportedly lack social and cultural capital. CRT is used to explain how racism is ingrained in our society and acknowledges a need for a fundamental redesign of power to deconstruct systemic injustices (Ladson-Billings and Tate 1995). From the understanding that CRT identifies the oppression built into institutions, CCW is utilized to identify how Communities of Color "survive and resist macro- and micro-level oppression" (Yosso 2005). CRT includes five tenets, one of which acknowledges the strength in the experiential knowledge within Communities of Color. Drawing from CRT's critique of racism and Bourdieu's theory of human capital, this community cultural

wealth framework acknowledges six forms of cultural wealth found in Communities of Color: linguistic, navigational, social, familial, resistant, and aspirational capital.

The six forms of cultural wealth are inherently interconnected. Linguistic capital is developed from communication experiences with more than one language or dialect and how it fosters intellectual and social skills, drawing from research in the field of bilingualism. Navigational capital represents the specific skills that people of color leverage to maneuver through social institutions, assuming those social institutions are not constructed with Communities of Color in mind. Social capital refers to the network of people and community that provide emotional and navigational support through society's institutions. Familial capital is understood as the cultural knowledge cultivated within the family including an understanding that family extends to the community and a commitment to community. Resistant capital reflects the knowledge and skills fostered through oppositional behavior to challenge inequity. Aspirational capital refers to the ability to maintain hopes and dreams beyond current circumstances even in the face of real and perceived challenges.

Altogether, CCW provides a framework to illuminate how underrepresented applicants to speech pathology master's degree programs make sense of their experience applying to graduate school. As a White-dominated field, it is crucial to analyze the field of speech pathology under the lens of CCW to identify the strengths and assets that underrepresented students bring with them into higher education, especially in the graduate school application process within their discipline. Using this framework, the research question is:

What forms of community cultural wealth do underrepresented undergraduate seniors in California access during the application process to speech-language pathology master's level programs?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, I utilize qualitative and quantitative methodologies to analyze survey data. Four surveys consisting of a series of closed- and open-ended items were disseminated over 12 months: (1) Pre-Application Perceptions: July-October 2021, (2) Application Preparation: November-December 2021, (3) Application Submission: January-February 2022, and (4) Post-Application Reflection: April-May 2022. The longitudinal nature of this study was selected to assess student experiences at different points across the application process. This study is part of a larger project and analyzes responses to one closed-ended and seven open-ended questions. The Institutional Review Board of California State University, Fullerton approved the study.

Participants & Procedure

Study participants received the survey from their undergraduate advisor and/or local chapter of the National Student Speech-Language-Hearing Association (NSSLHA) at 1 of the 17 American Speech-Language-Hearing Association recognized undergraduate programs in California. Ultimately, 12 institutions are represented in the study since the other five institutions either had no respondents or ineligible respondents. Of the 12 institutions, 11 are Hispanic Serving Institutions and/or Asian American Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions. Nine institutions are public universities and the other three are private universities.

I emailed the undergraduate advisors and NSSLHA chapters of each institution to disseminate the first survey to their students. Across the 17 universities, this survey was accessed 138 times where 88 eligible and consenting participants were identified from 12 institutions. These 88 participants received the next three surveys over the course of the study. These students were sent three email reminders per survey, for surveys two through four.

Participants were eligible for this study if they: (1) graduated in the Fall or Spring semesters of the 2020-2021 academic year and (2) intended or were unsure about applying to speech pathology graduate programs for matriculation in the following Fall semester after graduation. The demographic characteristics of these

Table 1. Survey Participant Demographics (N=88)

	n	%
Race/Ethnicity		
<i>American Indian/Alaskan Native</i>	0	0
<i>Asian</i>	8	9
<i>African American/Black</i>	6	6.8
<i>Hispanic/Latino</i>	32	36.4
<i>Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander</i>	2	2.3
<i>White</i>	24	27.3
First-Generation College	31	35.2
Low-Income Background	27	30.7
Transfer Students	25	28.4
Have Dependents	6	6.8
LGBTQ+	4	4.5
Adult Re-Entry/Nontraditional Student	3	3.4
DACA Recipient	1	1.1

Note. Percentages for race/ethnicity do not add up to 100 because students were able to select more than one category.

students are presented in Table 1. Participants received a multi-select question for racial/ethnic self-identification and an open-ended question where they shared any additional parts of their identity that they felt were crucial to understanding them. The majority of study participants identified as a Person of Color (73.7%). Additionally, a significant number of participants identified as a first-generation college student (35.2%), having a low-income background (30.7%), and being a transfer student (28.4%).

Data Analysis

The quantitative demographic data in this study exclusively came from the first set of questions that participants responded to between July and October 2021. These data were analyzed using basic descriptive statistics. Qualitative survey data were coded both by hand and with a digital analysis software package, *Nvivo*, to provide a valid analysis (Maher et al. 2018).

RESULTS

The analysis resulted in findings of how underrepresented applicants navigated the graduate school application process by employing the use of different types of cultural capital: linguistic,

navigational, social and familial, resistant, and aspirational. Student narratives provide insight into how these forms of capital worked together to drive applicants to commit to applying to graduate school through their social network and hope to one day practice as a clinician through culturally competent means. All quotes are reported in participants' words from the surveys.

Linguistic Capital: Bridging Bilinguals

Being bilingual is central to the identities and experiences of many participants, fueling their drive to become a speech-language pathologist, and thus, being closely tied to their aspirational capital. Furthermore, their desire to “increase bilingual representation in the field” is closely tied to resistant capital due to their personal experiences with linguistic injustices. Cognizant of the lack of linguistic representation in the field, speech pathology applicants are determined to bring their bilingual language skills to the profession to provide culturally sensitive services to their communities.

Experiences with linguistic racism activated participants' linguistic capital. Reflecting on her trajectory to becoming bilingual, one participant shared how her parents were discouraged from teaching her Spanish:

Educators early on discouraged my parents from speaking Spanish at home to ‘prevent confusion’ in our language development (SMH), which led me to internalize for a long time that my heritage was not worthy, and would impede my ability to succeed. Furthering my education (including in Spanish) allowed me to see not only the beauty, but the NECESSITY for me to be the SLP that fights for the affirmation of home languages, and fights against monolingual prescription.

Historically, monolingualism was promoted as the foremost practice for children's language development though current scholarship poses bilingualism as advantageous (Gunnerud et al. 2020; van den Noort et al. 2019). However, the effects of this previous philosophy to bilingualism pervades to the present day as educators and SLPs may discourage parents from speaking their heritage language with their children, causing dissonance in the family-

professional partnership (Lim and Cheatham 2021). Similarly, another participant shared her desire to provide bilingual services because of her family's experience with linguistic injustices:

Witnessing the impact that the language barrier has particularly in healthcare via my grandparents' delayed diagnoses drove me to be someone who contributes to bridging that language gap.

Ironically, the two settings where participants identified their personal occurrences of linguistic injustices are the two largest employment settings for SLPs: education and healthcare. This desire to serve bilingual communities stems from personal experiences with linguistic oppression. Participants shared how they transformed these negative encounters into motivation for pursuing a graduate degree to combat discrimination in their careers. In resisting the prevailing linguistic injustices, participants are intent on using their bilingualism to support their future clients.

Navigational Capital: Resilience through Resources

Graduate school applications include several components, many of which are unfamiliar to students who do not have family members who obtained graduate degrees. With their resourcefulness, applicants took advantage of pre-professional and campus resources to increase their knowledge of the application process. Additionally, students connected with professors and more experienced individuals in the field for encouragement and application support. Despite the historically exclusive nature of higher education, especially graduate-level degrees, students branched out and leveraged available resources to elucidate applications.

Two participants shared that they had a mentor through the ASHA Student to Empowered Professional (STEP) program. This virtual mentoring program was purposely created with underrepresented populations in mind. Considering only 2.6% of SLPs are Asian, one participant shared how she deliberately took advantage of the STEP program's mission: "I chose [my ASHA STEP mentor] specifically because she is also from an Asian-American background." In an e-

mentoring program for ethnically diverse student midwives, the program was highly beneficial for the mentees (Valentin-Welch 2016)—an experience similar to this participant since she gained comfort from the advice given to her by her professional mentor.

On-campus resources provided students with the opportunity to strengthen their applications. One first generation-Latina participant shared that her campus' Career Center was valuable for “general resume tips and how to approach drafting the Letter of Intent.” Furthermore, she elaborated on the benefits of her student support program and how the staff “helped a lot with general readability and editing for my resume and Letters of Intent.” She also described the importance of advisors and mentors within her support program. This combination of interactions and institutional support resonates with previous scholarship on the beneficial roles of counselors and support programs on success and persistence of Latino/a community college students (Tovar 2015).

Employing the assistance of more knowledgeable others was one strategy for applicants to seek help from. With the ability to proactively “build a network and meet professionals in the field who offered advice,” students demonstrated their utilization of navigational capital. One participant elaborated on this by sharing, “I overcame doubts by reaching out to others and networking with older people in this profession.” These older individuals spanned the educational-professional pathway as she recruited the help of SLP students, Ph.D. students in her lab, and current professionals. This student also revealed the emotional support her network provided. Another student found solace from her advisors. Responding to the question asking how the applicant overcame doubts during the application process, she named “Advisors who affirmed that I had done everything right, that I was a strong candidate, and that I should have confidence in myself” as a source of strength. To seek specific advice about a program, one

student shared that “admissions counselors from some private colleges I am applying to” as a valuable source of support, indicating that applicants understood where to access the information they sought. Other important individuals included professors and major advisors. Students used a wide range of people to get them through the applications.

With the goal of attending graduate school, participants formed their own networks to obtain the information essential to their ability to submit applications and hear words of affirmation important to their perseverance. These excerpts demonstrate the enterprising nature of underrepresented SLP applicants. This resourcefulness allowed them to enlist various resources and individuals to provide encouragement and advice throughout the application process.

Social and Familial Capital: Support from Connections within the Community

To navigate the challenging, and sometimes overwhelming, graduate school application process, applicants found support from their family and community. Having community support was vital to obtaining the resources and knowledge for applying and building their confidence in their applications. Participants found a wealth of social support from three domains: (1) mentors and friends in the field, (2) family and friends not in the field, and (3) mentors and resources through social media. This concept arose when asking who or what was instrumental in supporting the participant and asking how they overcame doubts during the process. These important individuals were all notably a part of their community, weaving together social and familial capital.

Mentors who have gone through the application process and friends concurrently going through the process alongside them provided a wealth of support. Participants especially emphasized people who come from minoritized backgrounds such as “those who are BIPOC”

and “culturally diverse minority women” as vital to their navigation. Finding support from those both in their field and community allowed applicants to feel seen and understand that they were not alone in the challenges that arose. Friends applying in the same application cycle shared a point of commonality with participants, thus providing a unique sense of understanding:

I found solace in speaking with my close friends about my worries, especially those who were going through the application process with me.

Even with the doubt and common imposter syndrome amongst underrepresented students, applicants developed a social network to cope with the stresses of applying. Beyond friends, interactions with mentors and advisors provided reassurance:

I also spoke with close mentors and advisors who affirmed that I had done everything right, that I was a strong candidate, and that I should have confidence in myself. Hearing affirmations from others’ confidence in me helped me with self-doubt a lot.

During this stressful period of applying, students developed a community that allowed them to lean on one another and hear from others about their accomplishment by applying.

Many participants highlighted the valuable social support from family and friends who were unfamiliar with graduate school and the field of speech pathology. Despite the lack of knowledge, they provided valuable social and emotional support. One participant shared:

Family supported as much as they could (mostly emotionally), but due to lack of familiarity with the process their support could only go so far.

While the support was important, the participant acknowledges its limited nature and went on to list the depth of support she received from her wide network. The socioemotional support alone was not enough to navigate applications, but participants utilized their navigational capital to find support within the discipline as well.

With the rise of COVID-19 during this application cycle, social media influencers and mentors were important to navigating the application process. Advice and mentorship through this virtual outlet came from people with similar underrepresented identities to the applicants:

I also utilized lots of resources and mentors that I would find out about through social media, such as @latinaGradGuide, and listening to presentations by first-generation students in higher education who shared their testimonies about their application process and how they got through.

In addition to graduate school influencers, students were resourceful and found support from “SLP students in Facebook groups.” Social media allowed for connections in a time where social interactions were limited, and even more limiting for students seeking connections within both their field and community, a statistically small population amidst the entire field of speech pathology. Despite the turmoil of a global pandemic, the virtual world increased the social network to tie students to mentors who understand their challenges in the application process.

Resistant Capital: Turn the Tide

Acutely aware of the lack of representation and the existing injustices in the field, participants had a strong conviction to impact the future of the profession through diverse representation and a clinical philosophy of providing culturally competent services. This desire to allow clients to see themselves in their clinician and to serve their future clients with culturally competent care often stemmed from personal experiences with linguistic or medical neglect. Resistant capital was most evident in applicants’ motivation to become a SLP.

By obtaining their graduate degree to begin their career as a SLP, current applicants will increase the diversity within the field. Participants understood the potential impact they would make on the field by entering the profession. One participant shared, “There are not enough Black SLPs so for me to be one and have a Black client would greatly impact me and hopefully

my client as well.” When asked to identify a meaningful experience that increased their confidence in pursuing graduate school, and describing how their identity related to it, another responded, “A meaningful experience is knowing that there are not many Native Hawaiians, or multiracial individuals like myself.” The influence that racially diverse healthcare providers have is substantial. Racial and ethnic concordance between patient and provider reaps benefits that combat healthcare biases. For Black, Latino, and Asian patients, racial concordance yields a modest positive association with overall health care satisfaction and respect in addition to increased likelihood in continual visits to their provider for ongoing medical issues (Ku and Vichare 2022; Ma, Sanchez, and Ma 2019). Especially since speech therapy clients have recurring therapy sessions with their SLP, racially underrepresented SLPs will provide more satisfying healthcare services over the duration of the treatment plan and will increase patient retention for their racially diverse clients. In addition to race, a transmasculine applicant similarly shared that “a professor who works in transgender voice therapy let me know that trans identities would likely be respected” when the applicant joins the field as a practicing clinician, indicating the need for gender diverse SLPs.

Social injustices entrenched in the field push applicants to resist the dominant practices to provide better services to Communities of Color. A marrying of her lived experiences with her learned knowledge of societal inequalities inspires one applicant to enter the field and challenge currently held standards of Eurocentrism:

Having learned of the great disparities in healthcare and education, and motivated by my personal experiences, I will always advocate for multilingualism and preservation of the heritage language and culture.

This participant’s experience with linguistic racism was earlier described in the previously mentioned linguistic capital. After her parents were advised to only speak to her in English as a child then continuing into college to develop her Spanish language

skills, she developed resiliency to challenge the linguistic expectations set upon her at an early age. Furthermore, this experience became a foundational value for her as she applied to graduate school and looked toward a career as an SLP. Although monolingualism was prescribed to her, she did not let that be the same for her future clients. Another participant's experience echoed this same sentiment:

I want to become a speech-language pathologist to help with bilingual services for bilingual children and adults, specifically Chinese families. My experience as a 1st-generation Chinese-American motivates me to become a SLP because my family has experienced racism and discrimination due to their broken English so I want to help others communicate and express themselves to their best ability.

As a witness to the discrimination her family faces, she developed a social justice orientation. Additionally, her drive to serve Chinese families like her own reflects her familial capital—her deep connection to community—and passing linguistic capital challenges the monolingual-English narrative. These applicants chose to activate their linguistic and aspirational capital in a fusion with a transformative form (Yosso 2005) of resistant capital, as their personal experiences fueled their drive to provide culturally sensitive and empowering services to their future speech therapy clients.

Enduring discrimination as a student of speech pathology also impacted self-efficacy for underrepresented students. An Asian participant described her experience sharing her graduate school aspirations with an advisor:

My white prof/advisor told me that I was not going to get into graduate school & become an SLP. Once I gave myself some time for it to decrease my confidence, I used it to fuel my ambition for pursuing this field.

This challenge with subordination is part of the dominant narrative for underrepresented students pursuing graduate education, yet this applicant displayed an active resistance to this narrative. Institutional agents including professors and advisors often serve in contradictory roles between empowering and gatekeeping (Stanton-Salazar 2011).

Overall, the applicants develop resistant capital in close ties with aspirational capital since they desire to challenge the norms of the field through transformative justice as a SLP. Additionally, they develop the necessary skills and knowledge to apply to graduate school, going against the advice given to them by White faculty and advisors.

Aspirational Capital: Hope for the Future and Self-Efficacy

As students apply to graduate school and prepare for their future, aspirational capital was deeply connected to the application process. As mentioned previously, participants felt a pull to provide improved services into their community drawing from linguistic, familial, and resistant capital. Stories of discrimination from their past or from their family members inspired applicants to become a clinician and do better for their clients. Delivering justice to future racially- and linguistically-diverse populations like themselves was one source of aspirational capital, but participants found this capital within their own drive to apply to graduate school and in their desire to provide better lives for their children.

Bringing representation into their communities is a significant hope for many applicants.

This theme especially came through for participants who desired to work in pediatric settings:

What motivates me is the fact that I can one day become a clinician that helps children that look like me, in hopes of inspiring and supporting them to the fullest extent.

With a lived experience growing up with limited representation, this Black applicant aspired to be a role model for the next generation of youth to demonstrate that they belong in a field like speech pathology and can acquire a graduate degree.

Applicants were not only driven to serve their communities as a SLP, but to actively bring justice into the field. A queer, first-generation African applicant explained:

What motivates me to become a speech-language pathologist is to be one in the growing population of SLPs that bring social justice, anti-ableism, and anti-racism to the field of speech-language pathology and audiology.

Since education is a form of resistance, participants were activating resistant capital by choosing to pursue higher education to gain entrance into a career where they can actively combat social injustices in their field. Pulling from their navigational capital, mentors served to empower their mentees, providing them with aspirational capital as they considered graduate school.

Something that increased my confidence pursuing graduate school was some of my mentors supporting the notions that things need to change in the SLP world and that I can be that change.

Instilling them with purpose and empowerment, mentors not only pushed students to apply to graduate school but cultivated their aspirational capital by telling their students that they can be the needed change in the field. Applicants not only believed in their ability to successfully apply to the graduate program but were left confident in their role to create change once they enter the field.

Pursuing a graduate degree in speech-language pathology was personal for many applicants as they were determined to achieve this goal for themselves. Even when the application towered over them, determination to obtain a graduate career in their desired field allowed them to surmount the challenge of applying:

My goal in becoming an SLP was paramount in continuing the application. I felt that I have come this far, I need to at least try.

Similarly, a Black participant shared, “I remembered how hard I worked and reminded myself that I earned my spot.” This dual form of aspirational and resistant capital emulates applicants’ certainty that they were capable of applying despite the educational barriers.

Applicants were not just mindful of their end goal but were also aware of what the end goal would mean for their family. For those with dependents, as well as those who

did not yet have dependents, applying to graduate school and becoming one step closer to their career goal would reap benefits for more than just themselves. This is evident in one applicant's explanation saying, "I also want to have Noh (*sic*) stability and be able to support my future family." Many student parents ascribed their motivation to their children and that the degree would "provide my daughters a better future." With the optimistic job outlook on the field, participants look forward to the financial stability that the career will provide for their descendants.

In summary, two participants' responses to their motivators for becoming a SLP encapsulates the sources of aspirational capital that participants divulged: "my children and helping my community" and "myself."

DISCUSSION

Applying to graduate school is a lengthy, daunting, and enigmatic process, especially for underrepresented students. This study contributes to the growing literature on underrepresented student experiences applying to speech-language pathology programs. However, this study is a small proportion of the scholarship that uses an assets-based approach. Since racially marginalized students in speech-language pathology programs remain underrepresented there is a need to examine their experiences, especially those who decide to pursue and continue their education in graduate school.

Primary findings from this study show that students utilized all six sources of capital from Yosso's (2005) framework: linguistic, navigational, social and familial, resistant, and aspirational. Using the community cultural wealth framework informs programmatic and policy changes to foster underrepresented students' cultural capital through the interwoven forms of capital.

Limitations

The sample for this study is based out of California with participants largely representing Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs). This may have influenced the amount of cultural wealth available to them. Underrepresented students at Predominantly White Institutions (PWIs) may amass cultural wealth in different ways and to a varied extent. Participant attrition was high considering its longitudinal nature with no direct benefits to participants. While the first survey yielded 88 participants, by the last survey only 15 participants responded. Participant participation is intrinsically driven, possibly by their dis/satisfaction with the application process and desire to see change in the field regarding support for underrepresented students.

Implications

By understanding the cultural capital that students access, appropriate practices can be adopted to foster cultural capital. Programs specifically designed for underrepresented students to develop community with peers and to connect with mentors foster navigational, social, resistant, and aspirational capital. Participants spoke in favor of ASHA's STEP e-mentoring program, indicating that increased resources should be allocated to the program to recruit more students and mentors. Additionally, students found community within their peers and friends of color also navigating the application process. Since most of the students attended MSIs, community was more readily accessible. Underrepresented students at PWIs may not have equal access to communities of color, so it is recommended that ASHA develops a virtual platform for underrepresented students across the country. Also, universities and communicative disorders departments should organize opportunities for students who are applying to graduate school to meet to exchange resources and empathize with one another.

Despite all participants being intent on or considering applying to graduate school at the beginning of the study in the first survey, at least two participants did not apply this cycle and decided to take a gap year. These two students continued to demonstrate their interest in the field. As a result, future studies should examine graduate school matriculation of those who have electively taken gap years prior to applying to determine the rate of attrition for students who take gap years and what factors led to this decision to take a gap year.

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APPENDIX: SURVEY QUESTIONS

Survey 1 Pre-Application Perceptions: July-October

- How do you racially/ethnically identify yourself as? (Select all that apply)
- Please share any additional parts of your identity that you feel are crucial to understanding you.

Survey 2 Application Preparation: November-December

- What motivates you to become a speech-language pathologist?
- How do you feel like race, or other aspects of your identity, has either positively or negatively impacted your experience as you approach the graduate school application process?

Survey 3 Application Submission: January-February

- Who or what has been instrumental in supporting and encouraging you through the application process?
- Who and or what supported your decision to apply to graduate school?
- What was a meaningful experience that increased or decreased your confidence in pursuing graduate school? How did your identity/identities relate to this experience?

Survey 4 Post-Application Reflection: April-May

- How did you overcome doubts or wavering of confidence during the application process?